

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B167
Date: 02 Feb 2006
Take Off 07:52:45
Landing: 09:56:04
Flight Time 2h03m19

Campaign: DABEX
Trials Instructions: Calibration flight for SWS, SHIMS and BBRs
Operating Area: Niamey area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ellie Highwood	University of Reading
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	SWS / SHIMS	Claire McConnell	University of Reading
9	Wet Neph / Mission Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
10			
11			
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B167 Track 02-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b167
 Date: 02 February 2006
 Project: DABEX
 Location: Niamey

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
072416		INU	0.79 kft	315	to nav
072511		GPS	0.79 kft	315	13' 28.65N 2' 10.53E
072611		cgps	0.79 kft	315	b167cgps.log
073425		video	0.79 kft	315	#1 dfc #2 ffc
075245		T/O	0.77 kft	085	Niamey
075850	080522	Profile 1	5.0 - 0.85 kft	299	50' (P1 interrupted during manouvre)
080523	082602	Profile 2	0.85 - 20.0 kft	082	50'
081452		P2 interrupt	10.0 kft	044	
081638		P2 resume	10.0 kft	277	
082858	083856	Run 1.1	20.0 kft	118	into sun
082927		heimann cal 14	20.0 kft	120	
084019	085020	Run 1.2	20.0 kft	034	cross sun
084043		heimann cal 10	20.0 kft	031	
084056		nev	20.0 kft	031	zero
085148	090149	Run 1.3	20.0 kft	303	down sun
090309	091511	Run 1.4	20.0 kft	217	cross sun extended 2 mins for sws
091543		!	20.0 kft	214	further ext for sws
091751		!	20.0 kft	214	extended R1.4 ends
091948	092107	Orbit 1	20.0 kft	174	170M turn to port
092200	092317	Orbit 2	20.2 - 20.0 kft	077	070M turn to port
092408	092522	Orbit 3	20.2 - 19.9 kft	089	120M turn to stbd
092615	092731	Orbit 4	20.1 - 19.8 kft	198	190M turn to stbd
092859	095108	Profile 3	20.0 - 2.4 kft	296	
093804		P3 interrupt	12.0 kft	296	
094020		P3 resume	12.0 kft	127	
095604		Land	0.76 kft	087	Niamey
100333		INU	0.78 kft	316	13' 29.51N 2' 09.45E
100440		GPS	0.77 kft	316	13' 28.65N 2' 10.53E

B167 Track 02-FEB-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DABEX: Calibration flight for SWS, SHIMS and BBRs

Flight No: B167

Date: 2nd February 2006

Trial objectives:

To perform high level patterns for SHIMS, SWS and BBR calibrations.

Location:

Over land areas in the region of Niamey.

Weather:

Cloudless skies essential.

Special requirements:

Low-level (50ft) flying over land (missed approach).

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Niamey.
2. Carry out a missed approach style ascent [5 mins, T= 5 mins]
3. Broken profile ascent to FL200 at 1000ft/min, breaking once at FL100 [20 mins, T=25mins]
4. Box pattern at FL200 consisting of 10 min legs orientated into, across, down and across sun [45mins, T=70 mins]
5. A series of four orbits at FL200, at maximum bank angle, two LH and two RH turns [10mins, T=80 mins]
6. Profile descent from FL200 to ~2000ft at 1000ft/min [20mins, T=120 mins]
7. Land Niamey. [10 mins, T=130 mins]

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B167

Date: 2nd February 2006

Sortie Objectives: DABEX high level calibration flight for radiometers.

Operating area: Over land to north of Niamey.

Weather: Clear skies. No cirrus. Considerable haze. Light winds

Flight Patterns:

Take off from Niamey at ~0750Z. Carried out a missed approach manoeuvre over Niamey airfield. Profile ascent, broken once at FL100, to FL200. Dust observed in lowest 3000ft with considerable fine structure. A very clear blue slot at around 4500ft was clear to all directions. On top of this, a deep biomass layer (CO strongly and positively correlated with nephelometer scattering persisted to around FL115. Another clear slot and then a very thin biomass layer between FL130 and FL145. Above FL150 we entered free tropospheric air with CO₂ and scattering reaching background values and O₃ increasing.

A box pattern consisting of into, across, down and across sun runs was performed at FL200. SHIMS and 1 module of SWS were recorded. SWS was stepped through 70 degrees from maximum possible tilt. SZA ~ 60°. During cross sun runs the SWS was pointed at zenith. All these were completely free of Ci. The final leg of the box pattern was extended to allow swapping of SHIMS and SWS modules on to the rack. Initially no signal was observed on the 2nd (near IR) module of SWS, but after 2 tries it was observed to be present but very small. A series of 4 orbits at bank angle 60° were performed (two left hand turns followed by two right hand turns).

A broken profile from FL200 (broken once at FL120) was performed and landed at Niamey at ~1005Z

Summary:

A very successful flight in cloud free skies, ideal for radiometer, SWS and SHIMS r calibrations. Two good vertical profiles of scattering and chemistry in addition.

Problems:

Upper pyrogeometer had problems at high altitude.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.1.6.7**.....

 Date **2nd Feb 06**.....

 Page **1** of

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
075245				Niamey	Clear skies overhead. No cloud visible. Somewhat hazy, Reduced science crew.
					Clear slot visible between 2 aerosol layers ~ 4kft.
075850	P1	5000ft ↓			Clear blue slot at 4000ft brown haze layer to north visible
080430	P1	1200ft			Fine structure visible in profile. Very strong peak (dust) at 2.8 kft.
080522	P1	50ft			
080522	P2	50ft ↑	89		Hazy
080901		400ft ↑			Very clear blue slot, dark haze above and below. to
081134		FL063 ↑			Strongish biomass peak, σ_g only 80 m^{-1}
081452	P2 int	FL400 →			Dust
081638	P2 restat	FL400 ↑			CO in biomass 250 ppb. Signal in O_3 .
081915	P2	FL110			top of main layer. thin layer visible above, ahead and to right.
082201		FL150			thin clear slot, some turbulence. SHMS, SWS check.
082413		FL180			Possibly another thin layer above was
0826	P2	FL200			ahead Free tropospheric air, CO_2 , O_3 , SO_2 ^{reph}
082858	R1.1	FL200 →	120	INTO sun	Clear above & below. Haze layer below

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.16.7**.....

 Date **2 Feb 06**.....

 Page **2** of

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
083856	R1.1end	FL200	120		cross distant to RHS, turn left
084019	R1.2	FL200	32	cross sun	SWS ~ zenith
085020	R1.2 end	FL200			
085148	R1.3	FL200	301	down sun	clear sky.
085918	R1.3	FL200	301	down sun	Some layers, thin, ahead Ci or ^{and} aerosol? ^{to} left
090149	R1.3end				CO calib in turn
090309	R1.4	FL200	216	cross sun	SWS ↑
090754	R1.4		216		Ci distant to left. thin and patchy
	R1.4end				
091948	01	FL200	170		SWS vis module only. LH turn
092107	01end	FL200			near IR was working but very small.
092200	02	FL200	070		LH turn
092317	02end	FL200			End orbit 2
	03				RH turn
092408	03	FL200	120		End orbit
092522	03				end orbit
092618	04	FL200	190		RH turn
092730	04	FL200			end orbit
092859	P3	FL200↓	297		start
093600	P3	FL140			clear thin layer dark above, clear slat visible, hazy below
093754	P3	FL120			Profile interrupt
094026	P3	FL120↓			restart P3 descending into dark haze
094?20	P3	2,300ft			End profile

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B167

Date: 2/2/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 2
--------------	---------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
07:58:50	200	0.11	Off													Start Profile 1 from FL050	
07:59:43	25	0.10	Off													FL040	
08:00:29	65	0.10	Off													FL030	
08:03:21	60	0.16	Off	Error												FL020	
08:05:23	200	0.12	Off	Error												End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 @ 50'	
08:07:00	75	0.21	Off	Error												FL020	
08:08:00	25	0.21	Off													FL030	
08:09:26	115	0.13	Off													FL040	
08:10:12	225	0.12	Off	10												FL050	
08:11:04	630	0.10	0	10												FL060	
08:11:54	525	0.10		5												FL070	
08:12:47	450	0.10		5												FL080	
08:13:42	290	0.11		5												FL090	
08:14:46	360	0.10		10												FL100	
08:17:42	280	0.10		5												FL110	
08:18:39	270	0.10		5												FL120	
08:19:42	80	0.10		2												FL130	
08:20:41	155	0.10		2												FL140	
08:21:40	25	0.12														FL150	
08:22:26	15	0.13														FL160	
08:23:18	10	0.10														FL170	
08:24:06	10	0.12														FL180	
08:24:58	6	0.11														FL190	
08:26:00	7	0.09														End of Profile 2 @ FL200	
08:28:58																Start Run 1.1 @ FL200	
08:29:00	10	0.12															
08:31:00	5	0.14															
08:33:00	10	0.13															
08:35:00	10	0.12															
08:37:00	15	0.14		5													
08:38:56																End of Run 1.1	
08:40:20																Start Run 1.2 @ FL200	
08:41:00	7	0.08															
08:43:00	6	0.13															
08:45:00	Noise																
08:47:00	5	0.09															
08:49:00	5	0.10															
08:50:22																End of Run 1.2	
08:51:50																Start Run 1.3 @ FL200	
08:52:00	8	0.13															
08:54:00	8	0.12															
08:56:00	8	0.11															
08:58:00	9	0.10															
09:00:00	5	0.10															
09:01:50																End of Run 1.3	
09:03:10																Start Run 1.4 @ FL200	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B167****Date:**

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	X X X	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	X X	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	X X X X X	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	X X X X X X X X X	Note the calibration file used cal27022006.txt Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour N
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	X X X X X X X X	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 0 seconds
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X X X X X	MDFE (final mod)
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?	n/a	No cloud
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B167

Date:

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	
6) In PVWAVE	X	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	Zero bad blocks
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	18490 blocks written
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit	X	
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	X	
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks <p style="text-align: center;">10</p> iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	X	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end.
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) File generation: Hit enter	X	
d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	X	
e) TAS: Y	X	
f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both	X	
0 unless either probe known to be faulty	X	
h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	X	
k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud	X	Note the particle type: 8
11 if known to be in water cloud	X	075230 z as start time
8 if known to be in mixed-phase	X	
8 if unknown	X	
l) Coefficient choice: 2	X	
m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	X	
10) In PVWAVE	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
i) enter:	X	
!PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'	X	
iii) exit	X	
11) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D	X	
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B167

Date:

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	X	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	Note the volume flow rate
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	X	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	X	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1	X	Bin 1 chosen
If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	X X	
e) Calibration volume flow rate:	X	1.6 ml/sec
Use the most recent value.	X	
Calibration files to be stored in ?????	X	
Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	X	
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	X	Zero seconds
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
3) In PVWAVE	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter:	X	
!PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat'	X	
,'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	X	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B167

Date:

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC				
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments		
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC				
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults				
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		Defaults in [square brackets] As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated		
2) Ftp transfer to BADC				
- stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary				

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B167****Date:**

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip) - rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 167

Date: 2nd February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	n
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	n
		AMS	n
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	n
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	n
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	n

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B167

Date: 2nd February 2006

Instruments

1. JW – not operated
2. Upper Pyrgeometer – signal and zero noisy, possible failure of unit or signal chain starts at 08:56 , recovered at 09:40
3. FFC window very mucky!

Cloud Physics – PCASP ok
FFSSP- switched off at low level,
2DC – ok
SID 2 noisy on occasions, otherwise ok
AMS & PAN – not operated
Wet Neph – Zero out of calibration
IR Camera – not operated
CCN, CVI, SWS, VACC – ok
SHIMS

Not fitted: ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls - Nil